

Charge Transfer Initiated Copolymerization of Styrene and Maleic Anhydride by *N*-Butylamine

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Copolymers of styrene and maleic anhydride with varying feed ratios have been synthesised by a charge transfer initiated mechanism using a mixture of *n*-butylamine and carbon tetrachloride in dimethyl sulphoxide at 60°. Reactivity ratios are calculated by Finemann-Ross and Kelen-Tüdös methods. The copolymers are characterised by ir and ¹³C nmr spectroscopy. The copolymers are mostly alternating and are hygroscopic. Thermal stabilities are checked by thermogravimetric analysis. Thermal degradations of the copolymers is a two-stage process, the major degradation being the first stage. The copolymers decompose at a lower temperature than polystyrene.

THERE has been an increasing interest in the initiation of homopolymerization¹⁻³ and copolymerization⁴⁻⁶ by charge transfer complexes. Free radical copolymerization of styrene (St) and maleic anhydride (MAN) has been extensively studied⁷⁻⁹. Kinetics of copolymerization of St/MAN system in dioxan¹⁰ and methyl ethyl ketone¹¹ have been studied. Monomer sequence distribution in St/MAN copolymers prepared by free radical mechanism has also been studied extensively¹². It might be interesting to find the sequence distribution in St/MAN prepared by CT mechanism and to study its thermal stability. Thermogravimetric (TG) study of PSt and its copolymers¹³ showed that from 300° onwards PSt undergoes a sharp weight-loss and by 418° the decomposition is complete.

Experimental

Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), *n*-butylamine (NBA), St and CCl₄ were of analytical grade and purified by standard procedures. MAN was purified by recrystallisation from chloroform and was dried under reduced pressure. Polymerization was carried out in vacuum ($\approx 10^{-5}$ mm/Hg)⁴ at 60°. The precipitated copolymers were dissolved in acetone-dioxan mixture (1 : 1, v/v) and reprecipitated in a mixture of petroleum ether and toluene (2 : 1, v/v). Percentage yield was determined gravimetrically. Reactivity ratios (r_1 and r_2) were calculated from data obtained for low conversion usually less than 10%, using Finemann-Ross (FR)¹⁴ and Kelen-Tüdös (KT)¹⁵ methods. Copolymer compositions were estimated by determining the anhydride content conductometrically¹⁶ with a Systronics 303 conductivity meter. In a typical experiment, the

copolymer (~ 0.2 g) was heated with aqueous 0.1*N* NaOH (30 ml) until completely dissolved. The alkaline solution was diluted to 250 ml with water and an aliquot (25 ml) was titrated conductometrically with 0.1*N* HCl. The statistical distributions of monomer sequence, St-St, MAN-MAN and St-MAN were calculated from well-known equations¹⁷. Using equations suggested by Ekpenyong¹⁸ mean sequence lengths (\bar{l}_1 and \bar{l}_2) were calculated. Intrinsic viscosity ($[\eta]$) was determined by a three-limb Ubbelohde viscometer at 30° in chloroform. The concentration of the solution for viscometric experiments was maintained so as to keep the ratio of efflux times for solution and solvent within 1.1 to 1.5. Since the bore of the capillary (0.4 mm) of the viscometer was very small, the solvent used being chloroform and the efflux time controlled, the kinetic energy correction could be neglected for practical purposes¹⁹.

Ir spectra of the copolymers were recorded with a Carl-Zeiss Specord 75 spectrophotometer. For ir spectra, films were prepared under vacuum from the solution of copolymers in chloroform.

¹³C nmr spectra were recorded by a Bruker WH-270 pulsed FT nmr spectrometer (67.89 MHz) using broad band proton decoupling. A chemical shift range of -10 to +240 ppm was used, taking the signal from deuteriochloroform as the reference (centre of triplet = 77.1 ppm from tetramethyl silane). A pulse width of 15 μ s and pulse repetition time of 2 s were used throughout.

TG was done using a Perkin-Elmer analyser in nitrogen at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ with 5 \pm 1 mg of powdered sample.

Results and Discussion

Copolymers of St and MAN at varying feed ratios had been prepared by a charge transfer mechanism³ using NBA and CCl₄ as initiators at 60° in DMSO. It was found that percentage yield decreased with increase in St content in the feed reaching a minimum at feed ratio [St]/[MAN] ≈ 5, then again the yield increased. The copolymers prepared from feed ratio higher than 5.5 did not dissolve in dilute alkali and swelled in acetone showing the formation of PSt also along with the copolymer.

Data for calculation of reactivity ratios by FR and KT methods are given in Table 1. The values calculated (confidence limit, CL) were, FR method : $r_1 = 0.033 \pm 0.003$, CL 90%, $r_2 = 0.004 \pm 0.002$, CL 60%; KT method : $r_1 = 0.032 \pm 0.002$, CL 95%, $r_2 = 0.003 \pm 0.002$, CL 50%.

TABLE 1—DATA FOR REACTIVITY RATIO CALCULATION BY FR AND KT METHODS

[NBA] = 1.06 mol dm⁻³, [CCl₄] = 2.06 mol dm⁻³,
[MAN] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³
 $\alpha = (F/MF_m)^{1/2} = 2.41$

$\alpha = [\text{St}]/[\text{MAN}]$	$b = d[\text{St}]/d[\text{MAN}]$	$F = a^2/b$	$G = a - (a/b)$	$\eta = G/(\alpha + F)$	$\xi = F/(\alpha + F)$
0.50	1.01	0.227	0.005	0.002	0.092
1.02	1.03	1.010	0.030	0.009	0.299
2.04	1.07	3.889	0.134	0.021	0.617
2.98	1.10	8.073	0.271	0.026	0.770
5.50	1.18	25.636	0.839	0.030	0.914
9.00	1.40	—	—	—	—
23.11	2.12	—	—	—	—

From structural data^{17,18} it was found that alternation St-MAN was more than 90% with negli-

gible blockness, MAN-MAN (≈0.2%). The alternating tendency of the copolymer was also shown by the product $r_1 r_2$ which approached zero. Negligible blockness with respect to MAN showed that MAN could not be homopolymerized by charge transfer mechanism. Blockness, St-St, in the copolymer increased as the St content increased in the feed. This might be due to the fact that PSt was also formed with the copolymer. Because PSt was formed, there was slightly higher mole fraction of St monomer (2.12 : 1) in the copolymer and an increase in yield when very high concentration of St was used in the feed (23 : 1).

The copolymer was hygroscopic as indicated by the ir spectra. When films were prepared in humid condition a marked shoulder at 1710 cm⁻¹ and broad band around 3400 cm⁻¹ were observed. The band at 1710 cm⁻¹ (along with anhydride peaks at 1760 and 1840 cm⁻¹) was attributed to the stretching vibration of carboxylic groups formed by the partial hydrolysis of the anhydride units. The absence of this band in the spectrum of the sample prepared under anhydrous conditions confirmed the hygroscopic nature of the copolymer.

Fig. 1 shows a typical ¹³C nmr spectrum of St/MAN copolymer with composition 1.03 : 1. Peak assignments were done as described elsewhere¹². The peaks centred at 175 ppm were due to the carbonyl carbon on the MAN units. The peaks at 137–145 ppm were due to C₁, the St aromatic carbon directly attached to the polymer backbone, while the peaks centred at 128 ppm were due to all other St aromatic carbons. Peaks at 41–43 and 51–53 ppm were for methine and methylene carbons respectively. Triad sequence distributions were

Fig. 1. ¹³C nmr spectrum of St co MAN prepared with NBA and CCl₄ with copolymer composition 1.03 : 1

calculated (Table 2) from relative peak intensities of the peaks in the C_1 region as done earlier¹². The

TABLE 2—TRIAD SEQUENCE DISTRIBUTIONS OF St/MAN COPOLYMERS

Composition = 1.03 : 1		
Triad	Chemical shift (ppm)	Relative peak area
MSM	137	0.89
SSM	138	0.04
MSS	142	0.04
SSS	144	0.02

number average sequence lengths from triad distributions with respect to St and MAN are 1.10 and 1.00 respectively. These values are comparable to the mean sequence lengths \bar{l}_1 and \bar{l}_2 . The errors in these monomer sequence distributions could be as large as 20% since the spectral signal-to-noise ratio was low and the peaks were not completely resolved. The sequence distributions indicated that the copolymer was mostly alternating having about 90% MSM triad along with $\approx 8\%$ SSM and MSS triad. The carbonyl region of the spectrum did not allow an analysis as straightforward as the C_1 region. The spectrum showed two peaks in the region. The tendency of MAN to add to itself in a growing polymer chain was so low that one could not expect MAN-MAN diads along the chain. Therefore, the only MAN centered triad is SMS. The two peaks at 174 and 176 ppm was probably due to the slightly different environments of the two MAN carbonyls. One carbonyl had the phenyl groups of the adjacent St unit attached to β and the other the phenyl groups attached to δ . Peak shoulders and broadening in this region were assumed due to different pentad structural units or to configurational difference along the chain.

Fig. 2 shows the TG traces in nitrogen atmosphere of PSt, MAN and their copolymers at varying compositions. PSt started a sharp weight-loss from 300° onwards and by 418° the decomposition was complete. Since MAN could not be homopolymerized by charge transfer mechanism the TG traces of MAN was recorded. It started sharp weight-loss around 150° and completed around 200°. The copolymers underwent two-stage weight-loss, the first stage corresponding to about 85% when composition was approximate 1 : 1. With higher St content the first stage weight-loss along with decomposition temperature increased. The copolymers decomposed at a lower temperature than PSt. The thermal stability of the copolymers decreased with the increase in MAN content in the copolymer. Since the compositions of the copolymers did not differ much, the thermal stabilities also did not differ appreciably. When the composition was 2.12 : 1, the stability was close to that of PSt. It is known that PSt decomposes mainly by depropagation and that the controlling factor in the mechanism of the degradation is the nature of the side-group attached to the carbon atom at which the chain-scission

Fig 2 TGA traces in nitrogen at a heating rate of $10^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for PSt, MAN and St co MAN at varying compositions: (—) PSt, (— × —) MAN, (---) St co MAN (1.18 : 1), (—) St co MAN (1.10 : 1) (---) St co MAN (1.01 : 1) and (.....) St co MAN (2.12 : 1).

occurs²⁰. In case of copolymers about 15% residue was left after 400°. This might be due to the result of thermal cyclisation of the anhydride units.

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